

**SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF IMMUNOGLOBULIN E IN VIRAL ALLERGO-DERMATOSES IN CHILDREN
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Annotation: Modern scientific achievements allow us to better understand the mechanisms of inflammation and the involvement of the immune system in the co-occurrence of allergic and infectious diseases. However, classical treatment regimens for allergic dermatoses are often ineffective in cases associated with viruses. Therefore, there is a need to search for new clinical and laboratory markers and methods of differentiated therapy. The issue of determining CMV/HSV status and immunological indicators, "...optimizing diagnostic methods for viral allergic dermatoses in early childhood" is becoming increasingly urgent and necessary.

Key words: synthesis of immunoglobulin E (IgE), cytokine.

**ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИММУНОГЛОБУЛИНА Е ПРИ ВИРУСНЫХ АЛЛЕРГОДЕРМАТОЗАХ У ДЕТЕЙ
ХУДАЙБЕРГАНОВ МУНИС РУЗИБАЕВИЧ**

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Аннотация: Современные научные достижения позволяют лучше понимать механизмы воспаления и участие иммунной системы в развитии сочетанной аллергической и инфекционной патологии. Однако классические схемы лечения аллергодерматозов зачастую неэффективны при вирусной этиологии. В связи с этим возникает необходимость поиска новых клинико-лабораторных маркеров и методов дифференцированной терапии. Вопрос определения ЦМВ/ВПГ-статуса и иммунологических показателей, «...оптимизации методов диагностики вирусных аллергодерматозов в раннем детском возрасте», становится всё более актуальным и востребованным.

Ключевые слова: синтез иммуноглобулина Е (IgE), цитокина.

**БОЛАЛАРДА ВИРУС БИЛАН БОҒЛИҚ АЛЛЕРГОДЕРМАТОЗЛАРДА ИММУНОГЛОБУЛИН Е УЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ
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Аннотация: Замонавий илмий ютуқлар алергик ва инфекцион касалликларнинг биргаликда кечишидаги яллиғланиш ва иммун тизими иштирокининг механизмларини чуқурроқ англаш имконини бермоқда. Бирок, алергодерматозларни даволашнинг классик

схемалари кўпинча вирус билан боғлиқ ҳолларда самарасиз бўлиб чиқмоқда. Шу боис янги клиник-лаборатор маркерлар ва дифференциалланган терапия усулларини излаб топиш зарурати туғилмоқда. ЦМВ/ВПГ-статусини ва иммунологик кўрсаткичларни аниқлаш, «...эрта ёшдаги болаларнинг вирус билан боғлиқ аллергодерматозларни ташхислаш усулларини оптималлаштириш» масаласи тобора долзарб ва зарур бўлиб қолмоқда.

Калит сузлар: иммуноглобулин E (IgE), цитокин, синтези.

Relevance of the topic. In recent years, classical treatment regimens for allergic dermatoses have often been ineffective in cases associated with viruses. Therefore, there is a need to search for new clinical and laboratory markers and methods of differentiated therapy. The issue of determining CMV/HSV status and immunological indicators, "...optimizing diagnostic methods for viral allergic dermatoses in early childhood" is becoming increasingly urgent and necessary.

Purpose of the study. The results of a comprehensive immunological and allergological examination of young children with virus-associated allergic dermatoses are presented.

Results and discussions: In general, the results of the study of the level of immunoglobulin E (IgE) in the blood serum of patients showed that IgE synthesis was activated in children with allergic dermatitis. This confirms the allergic nature of dermatitis and the important role of immunological sensitization in its development.

Figure 1. Immunoglobulin E levels in allergic dermatitis in children

To differentiate between virus-related and classic forms of allergic dermatitis, a thorough analysis of maternal allergy history, obstetric history, and clinical signs of dermatitis in children was performed. The study results revealed high reactivity to the following allergens in group 1 children aged 0-12 months:

Food allergen mixture

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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(f20–f25–f33–f44–f84–f87–f92–f95: almond, tomato, orange, strawberry, kiwi, melon, banana, peach) — 4.5 ± 0.29 IU/ml

Egg protein (f1) — 4.0 ± 0.09 ME/ml

Egg yolk (f75) — 4.7 ± 0.1 ME/ml

Cow's milk (f2) — 5.6 ± 0.09 ME/ml

A mixture of fish allergens

(f3–f41–f205–f206–f254: cod, salmon, herring, mackerel, flounder) — 5.3 ± 0.28 ME/ml

A mixture of vegetable allergens

(f12–f15–f25–f31–f35: peas, beans, tomatoes, carrots, potatoes) — 5.7 ± 0.18 ME/ml

Moderate reactivity

Grain products

(f4–f6–f7–f8–f9: wheat, barley, oats, corn) — 3.9 ± 0.13 IU/ml

Low reactivity (in cases associated with CMV + herpes)

Fruit mixture

(f49–f92–f94–f95: apple, banana, pear, peach) — 0.7 ± 0.02 IU/ml

Wheat (f4) — 0.5 ± 0.01 IU/ml

Rice (f9) — 0.6 ± 0.01 IU/ml

Conclusion (Group 1): Children with allergic dermatitis associated with CMV and herpes infections have different levels of reactivity to allergens, indicating a complex mechanism of pathogenesis. These results demonstrate the need for differential assessment of pathological conditions and comorbid conditions.

Allergic sensitization spectrum (group 2, 1–3 years)

It was found that reactivity to allergens increased with age. In addition to the allergens identified in children in group 1, the following sensitization was detected in children in group 2:

House dust mixture (m1–m3–m5–m6–d1–d2–h1) — 1.3 ± 0.04 IU/ml;

Grasses (g3–g4–g5–g6–g8) — 1.4 ± 0.54 IU/ml

Weeds (w1–w6–w7–w10–w19) — 2.7 ± 0.68 IU/ml

Bovine epithelial allergen (e4) — 1.3 ± 0.1 IU/ml

Conclusion (group 2): In children aged 1–3 years, the sensitization spectrum expanded, and reactivity to object, airborne, and animal allergens was observed. This reflects the progressive development of the allergic process with age and hyperactivity of the immune system against the background of viral infections.

Conclusions: Based on the results obtained, a step-by-step differential diagnostic algorithm was developed. The algorithm is based on the history of the mother and child, clinical signs, SCORAD scale, the presence of IgM/IgG against CMV/HSV, serum IgE levels, allergy panel results, and risk factor assessment.

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THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-11

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